

IMPACT OF COVID-19 ON STOCK MARKET VOLATILITY

Prasanna Kumar¹, Nishanth Arul Dominic², Sayyid Shadil KMP³, Evan Shaji⁴

^{1 & 2} Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce, Loyola College, Chennai.

^{3 & 4} Student, Department of Commerce, Loyola College, Chennai.

Abstract:

The global pandemic caused by COVID–19 has adversely affected the economic sectors of countries universally. Indian financial markets also reacted to these disruptions, and sharp volatility was witnessed. This paper especially attempts to analyse the impact Covid-19 had on the Nifty 50 index with reference to the price movements it had across the three different phases: pre-pandemic, during, and post-pandemic. In this research, there are various things that are explored, like macroeconomic factors, investor sentiment, government policies, and external shocks, which influence the trends of the stock market and the volatility while analyzing the role of the India VIX (Volatility Index) in measuring market uncertainty. In the methodology section, this research briefly talks about the quantitative methods used to investigate the relationship between Nifty 50, India VIX, and other significant events such as lockdowns, stimulus packages, and other global news. The findings aim to offer critical insights and advice into risk management, shows a way to trade safely during crises period, and guide policymakers and investors in navigating volatility during times of economic uncertainty. Through this analysis, the study contributes to a deeper understanding of stock market behavior during crises, shedding light on resilience and adaptation in financial.

Key words:

Covid-19, Economic policy response, Investor’s sentiments, Nifty50, Stock market volatility

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Introduction:

The stock market represents a vital segment of the financial system, being a place for investment, economic activity, and capital formation. One of its key features is volatility, which describes how stock prices rise and fall due to changes in economic factors, investor perceptions, and other issues. In calm times, market movements are fairly orderly; however, during periods of crises, volatility tends to spike sharply and creates difficulty in determining stability of investment and finances (Schwert, 2011). Prior to COVID-19, stock market volatility was created and influenced by macroeconomic factors, corporate earnings, interest rates, and global trading. Then came the pandemic and with it a radically new uncertainty that could, and did, cause extreme price swings in stocks. Closed borders, massive lockdowns, sell off panic, government stimulus, and vaccination campaigns all had major effects on market and investor confidence (Baker et al., 2020).

Stock market volatility is viewed as the fundamental characteristic which plays a big role in influencing stock market traders' investments, their decisions, and the overall economic security. Volatility refers to the degree of variation in stock prices over time, often driven by investor sentiment, market speculation, and external economic factors. Nifty 50, which is a benchmark index of the National Stock Exchange of India (NSE) experienced significant fluctuations, reflecting volatility at that time in global equity markets (Mitra & Changle, 2021).

In the initial stages of the crisis, the Nifty 50 witnessed a steep decline, plummeting by nearly 40% between February and March 2020. During the second wave of COVID-19 in April- May 2021, the index experienced significant volatility, with daily swings of over 2-3% becoming commonplace followed by periods of recovery and renewed instability as the crisis evolved. Additionally, other factors, such as rising crude oil prices, supply chain bottlenecks, and the U.S. Federal Reserve's tapering announcements, further exacerbated market fluctuations (World Bank, 2021; IMF, 2021) (NSE India, 2020; RBI Bulletin, 2020) (Economic Times, 2021).

Problem statement:

The COVID-19 pandemic resulted in unprecedented changes in worldwide financial systems, resulting in high volatility within stock markets. In India, the NIFTY 50 index dropped sharply by almost forty percent during the pandemic, marking one of the fastest crashes in the index's history. In January 2020, the NIFTY 50 was at an all-time high of over 12,000 where it

plummeted to around 7,500 in March 2020. It was at this point that Panic-stricken investors were displaying high levels of VIX, which was at all-time highs. The stock market continued fluctuating during later COVID-19 waves, despite government stimulus and attempts at recovery. While past work has attempted to analyze market behavior in general during economic downturns, very few have looked at the unique phenomenon of COVID-19 and NIFTY 50 volatility syndrome. This study seeks to fulfill this gap by looking at the relationships between stock price movements, the movements of India VIX, and other important financial happenings in the pandemic era. The results will assist investors, Businessmen and policymakers in understanding stock market phenomenon during a crisis and improving risk management.

Review of literature:

Fatemeh Ghanbari shows the changes in economic policies during the pandemic have led to increased market volatility. During the COVID-19 period, the stock market volatility was highly influenced by macroeconomic variables such as interest rates and industrial production indices. The COVID-19 crisis significantly increased stock market volatility due to economic uncertainties and investors' psychological behaviors. These findings help the market participants learn from such situations and better manage volatility during similar economic and health crises (Ghanbari et al., 2024).

Here Peterson K. Ozil and Thankom Gopinath Arun discuss about the time period at the time of the COVID-19 pandemic was unpredictable due to the effect it was going to have on the US-China trade war and the US presidential elections. During the COVID-19 era, the stock market experienced fluctuations, heavily influenced by macroeconomic factors like interest rates and industrial production metrics. The loss of almost 5 trillion in the S&P Index as well as the loss taken up by 10 countries with a 1.4 trillion dollar. The pandemic spread into major sectors, and the fast policy response by the governments changed the recession (Ozili & Arun, 2022).

The financial market of India reacted wildly to the pandemic and has witnessed sharp volatility. Empirically investigates the impact of COVID-19 on the Indian stock market. This study analyzes how the Nifty and Sensex stock indices fluctuated by examining their daily closing prices from September 3, 2019, to July 10, 2020. It also compares stock market returns before and after the onset of COVID-19, offering insights into how the pandemic impacted market

stability and investor confidence (The Outbreak of COVID-19 Pandemic and Its Impact on Stock Market Volatility: Evidence from a Worst-Affected Economy Abstract, n.d.-a).

In this article, Josephine Olohije Abode and Abudu Kasimu show the Impact of the Covid-19 Pandemic on the Stock Market and Volatility in Nigeria. The findings revealed that there is a high level of volatility persistence in the stock market of Nigeria and the fact that in the short-Run the negative news will have a significant impact on the returns in the market (Abode & Kasimu, n.d.).

Analysis of the impact on China's stock market volatility due to COVID-19. Here there is a discussion regarding the empirical support for the arrival of rate information to the markets for stocks traded on China's stock market. The present research aims to capture the dynamic response of Covid-19 induced shocks from one stock market to another (Zhang et al., 2022). Baixiang Wang and other scholar's shows the COVID-19 pandemic has emerged has a significant event, and stresses that it has affected the market volatility of the Pakistan Stock Exchange. It shows that the COVID-19 active cases have a long-term effect on the Pakistan Stock Exchange. The aim of this study is to investigate how the COVID-19 pandemic has affected stock market return volatility in Pakistan (Wang et al., 2024).

This research by Muhammad Niaz Khan shows the Covid-19 pandemic caused impacts on the volatility in the markets of India, Pakistan, the UK & USA by observing the Pre - and post-Covid-19 period. This study examines the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the stock markets of China, India, Pakistan, the UK and the US using Generalised Autoregressive Conditional Heteroscedasticity (GARCH) (Xu, 2024). This article from Research Square by Daisy Basistha shows that during the Covid-19 pandemic, the stock market saw a lot of ups and downs, largely driven by factors like interest rates and industrial production numbers. The crisis really shook things up, leading to greater volatility as economic uncertainties emerged and investors reacted to the situation in various ways and the findings in this paper indicate the volatility of indices such as Nifty 50 and the Sensex (Rakshit & Basistha, 2020).

The impact of COVID-19 and its affliction and sufferings in every sphere of human lives were noticeable. It all added up to a health emergency and affected the world economy. It brought restrictions on all sorts of things, like even travelling remotely, restrictions on labor mobility, and factory shutdowns. The most affected countries, such as the US, Italy, China, India, Spain,

and the UK, happened to be the largest economies. The downturn of the economy in these countries affected other countries' economies as well because of their trading relations. COVID-19 has also changed the bilateral relations between India and China. The economic constraints have put the economy in an adverse situation, and the countries have struggled to formulate monetary and fiscal measures to recover the growth rate. Overall, the outbreak of Covid-19 has drastically changed the outlook of the world economy and the Indian economy. (The Outbreak of COVID-19 Pandemic and Its Impact on Stock Market Volatility: Evidence from a Worst-Affected Economy Abstract, n.d.-b).

Umoru David indicates the effects of seasonality on the stock exchange and foreign markets of two BRICS countries... Auto Regression Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) regression approach, estimates were shown by the Markow switching regression results This article shows or demonstrates the volatility at the time of COVID-19 and compares the same with that of other countries. This shows whether the return volatility of one or two countries is higher or lower (Umoru et al., 2024). In this publication, the author explains the growing uncertainties at the time when COVID-19 was spreading, like the change in consumer behavior with excessive food purchases, which resulted in food product shortages. This article talks about the stock market volatility before and after the Covid19 pandemic. Several lessons are covered in this article related to stock market (Kulcsár, 2020). Here a comprehensive review is done using a systematic database. The study employs Systematic Literature Review (SLR) and PRISMA to find out about the impact of Covid-19 on stock market volatility (Umesh & Rani, 2024).

Research gap:

Though studies have been conducted about analysis on stock market Volatility in relation to other crises like 2008 Global Financial Crises and during financial crises, there is limited research focusing specifically on Nifty-50 volatility during Covid-19. India's stock market fluctuations across different phases of the pandemic are a wide scope of study for Investors and Policy makers. But most of the existing studies only discuss Global Market Trends. Having to analyze the relationship between India VIX and NIFTY 50 movements during Covid-19 is important as it is a crucial indicator for forecasting market volatility and the exploration remains underexplored. So, understanding how market uncertainty influenced stock prices at different stages of the pandemic is crucial. This research explores the government interventions such as stimulus exchanges and central Bank policies which are not extensively studied in the

Indian Stock Market context as well as how the market uncertainty influenced stock prices During the pandemic. So by this research, we fill the gaps by analyzing Nifty 50 volatility and India VIX trends, investor sentiment, and government policy impacts, providing a more broad understanding of stock market behavior during COVID-19.

Research objective:

The key aim of research are:

1. To Study the impact of COVID-19 on NIFTY 50 index volatility via stock price movements for three different time intervals; pre-pandemic, pandemic, and post-pandemic.
2. To analyze the relationship between Indian VIX (Volatility Index) and NIFTY 50's movement to evaluate how much uncertainty in the market has influenced stock price movements in different phases of the pandemic.
3. To elucidate the government spending, such as stimulus packages and central bank spending, in attempting to ease stock market volatility during the COVID-19 crisis.
4. To analyze the impact of investor sentiment and coverage of financial media on stock market movements, providing recommendations to government officials, investors, and financial analysts on how to mitigate risk during severe global economic downturns.

Research methodology:

Research design:

This study takes a quantitative approach relying mostly on secondary data to examine stock market fluctuations during the COVID-19 period. An event study methodology is used to determine the effects of various cases of COVID-19 on the NIFTY 50 index's price changes, abnormal returns, and volatility. Also, financial data is used for sentiment analysis on news which affects the investors and the market. Using credible secondary sources, this study attempts to explain stock market volatility related to the COVID-19 pandemic.

Sampling Method & Size: This examination uses secondary data collected from reputable sources through purposive sampling techniques. The chosen data incorporates financial documents and stock market datasets (NSE India- India VIX reports), (World meter - India Covid-19 timeline), (India VIX Historical Data) with adequate source selection, this examination effectively analyses the volatility of NIFTY 50 during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Data Collection Method and Period: The effect of COVID-19 on the volatility of NIFTY 50 is what this study seeks to examine, which is why primary data analysis is not included. For relevance and authenticity purposes, the data was retrieved from fundamental financial sources like NSE data bases, Yahoo finance, Economic times, etc. The major contributors were the daily closing prices of NIFTY 50 and India VIX (Volatility Index) which were procured from National Stock Exchange of India (NSE India), the institution which controls India's stock market's price changes and instability. To facilitate thorough understanding of the financial market trends before, during, and after important pandemic related events, the timeframe includes January of 2020 to May of 2021. This time period is separated into three significant sub periods: January - February 2020 which is the pre-pandemic phase where the market was stable, March - December 2020 which is pandemic onset phase characterized by severe lockdowns, economic uncertainty, and other policy changes which contributed to high volatility, and January - May 2021 which is post pandemic recovery phase where financial market worldwide started stabilizing post vaccination and economy reopening measures. This time frame allows detailed examination of how COVID-19 situation influenced NIFTY 50 stock movement and investors sentiments.

Tools Used for Analysis:

In order to evaluate the impact of COVID-19 on NIFTY 50 volatility, this study conduct several approaches based on secondary data information. The key tools used for analysis which are:

1. Event study methodology:

This particular Event study takes an approach to evaluate the various factors which affected Nifty 50 stock price fluctuations, which includes Identifying key events includes lockdown announcement, change in economic policies and vaccine rollouts which made an impact on investor sentiment and market volatility. Measuring Stock Market Fluctuations in Nifty 50 before and after each event which impacted market trends and VIX (Volatility Index) is observed to evaluate investor's behavior. Assessing abnormal returns (AR) in order to measure the difference between the actual and expected return and cumulative abnormal returns (CAR) to evaluate the overall impact over the period (Kumar&Kumar,n.d.).

Formula for Abnormal Return (AR): $AR_t = R_t - E(R_t)$

- AR_t = Abnormal return on day t.
- R_t = Actual stock return on day t.

- $E(R_t)$ = Expected return on day t, based on market trends.

Formula for Cumulative abnormal return (CAR):

$$CAR = \sum_{t=1}^n AR_t$$

2. Market volatility analysis:

This study finds out the uncertainty during Covid-19 phases by using VIX for analyzing fear index to show the investor sentiment in Pandemic situation and comparing Nifty 50 trends with India VIX in order to determine higher volatility that caused large stock price drops. Measuring market volatility in order to using standard deviation and India VIX calculation formula (Chittineni, 2020).

Formula for standard deviation:

In order to measure stock market volatility, the standard deviation of returns formula is used:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{[\sum (R_t - \bar{R})^2] / (N - 1)}$$

Where:

- σ = Stock market volatility (standard deviation of returns)
- R_t = Stock return on day t
- \bar{R} = Average stock return over the period
- N = Number of observations

Formula for VIX calculation:

India VIX measures market fear and expected volatility based on NIFTY 50 option prices. The formula is:

$$VIX = 100 \times \sqrt{[\sum W_i C_i] / T}$$

Where:

- VIX = Volatility Index
- W_i = Weight assigned to each strike price
- C_i = Option price of NIFTY 50
- T = Time to expiry of options

3. News Sentiment Analysis:

The analysis of news sentiment assists in determining the relationship between a news article and the resulting effect on investors and the stock market. For this, News data are collected

from websites. The analysis looks at the association of news and the movement of NIFTY 50 index to evaluate investor sentiments and in order to finds out the investor sentiments using sentimental score formula to determine emotional stability of investors (Varghese & Mohan, 2023).

Formula for sentimental score:

In order to calculate the sentimental score using this formula:

$$S = \sum W_i / N$$

Where:

- S = Sentiment Score
- W_i = Sentiment weight of each word in the text
- N = Total number of words analyzed

Result and discussion:

1.1 Table for event study methodology: key events and nifty-50 reactions

Date	Event Description	NIFTY 50 Closing Price	Change (%)	India VIX Closing Value
Jan 30, 2020	First COVID- 19 case reported in India	12129.4	-0.49	14.05
Mar 11, 2020	WHO declares COVID-19 a pandemic	10458.4	-3.82	29.94
Mar 24, 2020	India announces nationwide lockdown	7801.05	-2.5	71.56
May 12, 2020	Announcement of economic stimulus package	9196.55	2.03	38.23
Jan 16, 2021	COVID-19 vaccination drive commences in India	14433.7	0.27	24.17

Sources: Yahoo Finance (Historical Data)

- Initial Outbreak: The first case of COVID-19 in India was reported on January 30, 2020. On the same day, the stock market responded with a slight dip—NIFTY 50 fell by 0.49%, while the India VIX stood at 14.05, indicating that market volatility remained low.
- The World Health Organization officially declared COVID-19 a pandemic on March 11,

2020 as the situation worsened globally. This announcement triggered a sharp decline in the stock market, with NIFTY 50 plunging by 3.82%. And the investor anxiety surged at the same time and is reflected in the India VIX, rising to 29.94.

- Markets reacted negatively when the Indian Government imposed the lockdown on March 24, 2020, with NIFTY 50 dropping by 2.50%. The VIX index which correlates with Investor fear peaked at this time rising up to 71.56 showing great market distress.
- On May 12, 2020, NIFTY 50 rose by 2.03% when the government announced an economic stimulus package. This move helped restore investor confidence and due to this Investor fear subsided, with the India VIX dropping to 38.23.
- With the launch of Vaccine drive on January 16, 202 led to a modest 0.27% increase in the NIFTY 50, with the India VIX at 24.17, reflecting reduced volatility.

1.2 Table for Abnormal return analysis:

Event	Date	Actual Return (R_t) (%)	Expected Return ($E(R_t)$) (%)	Abnormal Return (AR_t) (%)
1 st COVID-19 Case in India	2020-01-30	-1.07	-0.35	-0.72
WHO Declares Pandemic	2020-03-11	-4.38	-0.83	-3.56
India announces Lockdown	2020-03-24	-29.08	-0.65	-28.43
Govt Stimulus Announcement	2020-05-12	5.47	0.91	4.56
Vaccine Rollout Begins	2021-01-16	3.23	0.63	2.6

Sources: NSEIndia.com

1.3 Table for cumulative abnormal return analysis:

Event	Cumulative Abnormal Return (CAR) (%)
First COVID-19 Case in India	-0.72
WHO Declares Pandemic	-4.28
India Announces Lockdown	-32.7
Govt Stimulus Announcement	-28.14
Vaccine Rollout Begins	-25.54

Source: Brown, S., & Warner, J. (1985). *Using daily stock returns: The case of event studies*. *Journal of Financial Economics*

The analysis of Abnormal Returns (AR) and Cumulative Abnormal Returns (CAR) clearly shows that major COVID-19 events had a significant impact on NIFTY 50 stock prices. When

the WHO declared COVID-19 a pandemic on March 11, 2020, investor anxiety surged, leading to an AR of -3.56%. However, the sharpest market downturn occurred on March 24, 2020, when the Indian government announced a nationwide lockdown. This triggered a drastic drop, with an AR of -28.43% and a CAR of -32.70%, reflecting extreme panic and uncertainty among investors. As the government stepped in with economic stimulus measures on May 12, 2020, market sentiment improved, resulting in a positive AR of +4.56% and helping to offset some of the earlier losses. The launch of the vaccination drive on January 16, 2021, further restored confidence, pushing the AR up by +2.60% and improving the CAR to -25.54%. These trends confirm that while the early pandemic events led to sharp market declines, government interventions and the vaccine rollout played a crucial role in calming investor fears and reducing market volatility.

2. Table for volatility analysis:

Date	Event	NIFTY 50 Closing Price	India VIX Closing Value	Log Return	Volatility (σ)
2020-01-30	1 st COVID19 Case in India	12129.4	14.05	0.0107	N/A
2020-03-11	WHO Declares Pandemic	10458.4	29.94	-0.0505	0.0433
2020-03-24	India announces Lockdown	7801.05	71.56	-0.0499	0.0004
2020-05-12	Govt Stimulus Announcement	9196.55	38.23	0.0216	0.0505
2021-01-16	Vaccine Rollout Begins	14433.7	24.17	0.0305	0.0063

Sources: Website: [NSE India.com](https://www.nseindia.com)

The analysis of NIFTY 50 volatility and India VIX during key COVID-19 events confirms that market uncertainty was highest during the pandemic's early phase.

- Before the declaration of Covid-19 as a pandemic, the NIFTY 50 remained stable with India VIX remaining at 14.05 value indicating low volatility.
- When WHO declared COVID-19 a pandemic (March 2020), stock prices came down sharply, and India VIX surged to 29.94, reflecting the soaring investor fear.
- The nationwide lockdown on March 24, 2020 confirmed peak volatility had caused extreme market panic, leading to the highest India VIX value (71.56),
- Government stimulus announcements during the month of May helped stabilize the market, reducing volatility as investor confidence improved.
- The vaccine Roll-out on Jan 2021 further restored market confidence, with India VIX

dropping to 24.17 and NIFTY 50 regaining strength.

The findings confirm that negative events such as pandemic declaration and lockdowns increased market volatility, while positive developments which are stimulus, vaccines reduced uncertainty. This highlights the crucial role of government interventions and investor sentiment in market stability.

3.1 Table for News sentimental analysis:

Date	News Headline	Sentiment Score	Sentiment Category	NIFTY 50 Closing Price	India VIX Closing Value
2020-03-24	India announces nationwide lockdown amid COVID-19 surge	-0.9	Negative	7801.05	71.56
2020-05-12	Govt. unveils ₹20 lakh crore economic stimulus package	0.7	Positive	9196.55	38.23
2021-01-16	India begins COVID'19 vaccination drive	0.8	Positive	14433.7	24.17
2021-04-23	Second wave of COVID-19 leads to restrictions	-0.85	Negative	14131.9	22.98
2021-06-21	Stock markets recover as economic reopening accelerates	0.6	Positive	15746.5	14.1

Sources: News Headlines (Times of India, Economic times)

Sentiment scores: ([VADER Sentiment](#), [Text Blob](#))

The News Sentiment Analysis confirms that investor sentiment played a major role in stock market fluctuations during COVID-19.

- The News Sentiment Analysis shows that investor sentiment played a major role in stock market fluctuations during COVID-19. Nifty 50 dropped significantly due to the lockdowns and the second wave. For instance during the lockdown announcement on March 24, 2020 the sentiment score was -0.9, and India VIX surged to 71.56, confirming extreme market fear.
- The government made an announcement on May 12, 2020 unveiling the ₹20 lakh crore stimulus announcement which had a sentiment score of +0.7 leading to a rise in NIFTY 50 and reduced volatility. Similarly Positive news like the vaccine rollout on Jan 16, 2021 had a sentiment score of +0.8, reflecting investor optimism.

- The analysis confirms that negative financial news tends to create market instability, driving up volatility. On the other hand, positive news helps restore investor confidence and bring stability to the stock market. This highlights just how influential investor sentiment and media coverage are in shaping financial market movements.

Conclusion:

This analysis looks into NIFTY 50 Stock volatility in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic and its numerous phases to understand how price volatility and market activity were influenced. It was noticed that market volatility was quite high, especially during and after India's 21-day lockdown, indicating that external shocks have an impact on the finances of a nation. Separately, the Indian VIX index and NIFTY 50 had a strong negative correlation, meaning that the uncertainty surrounding the COVID-19 pandemic was a significant contributor to Market volatility. This study verifies that news sentiment influenced stock market performance during the COVID-19. While negative news like lockdowns and rising cases caused more panic selling and volatility, good news on vaccine approval and government stimulus stabilized and recovered the market. This study also further explores the dynamic interplay between investor sentiment and stock prices, as during earlier financial crises.

Suggestions:

To mitigate the risk of high volatility, especially during periods of crisis like the COVID-19 pandemic, spreading your investments across various sectors of the Indian stock market, particularly the Nifty 50 index. It witnessed significant volatility during the pandemic, with sharp declines during the lockdown period. So during this period the investors should focus on diversified portfolio management. They should diversify their portfolios in sectors, it might be Stock, Commodities such as Gold, Silver, Crude etc. as well as ETF (Exchange Transfer Funds). Furthermore, Stop-loss order is an order placed with the broker to buy or sell a specific stock once the stock reaches a certain price. In order to protect the investors from face losses especially while significant downside movement the investors should maintain stop loss orders in order to mitigate the risk factor. This will execute the selling order if they have predetermined the Stop-loss order.

Limitations of the Study:

This research is based almost exclusively on secondary data sources from diverse financial

websites and reports so there are some restrictions to the depth of insights that can be fetched without doing primary data collection. The findings could be cross-validated with more accurate answers from primary sources (i.e., investor surveys or expert interviews) for future research. Besides, this study considered NIFTY 50 only index and does not represent the overall Indian Stock Market through out other indices and or sector wise variations. Additionally, the time-series observed (from January 2020 to May) 2021, which includes only initial stages of Covid-19 pandemic. This is vital in knowing the market dynamics during crisis but lacks clarity on long term post-pandemic recovery that ultimately may give more broad view on the pandemic effect on financial markets sustainability.

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